

Stellar atmospheric parameters and chemical abundances of ~ 5 million stars from S-PLUS multi-band photometry

(Supplementary Material)

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ABSTRACT

Context. The APOGEE, GALAH, and LAMOST spectroscopic surveys have substantially contributed to our understanding of the Milky Way by providing a wide range of stellar parameters and chemical abundances. Complementing these efforts, photometric surveys that include narrow/medium-band filters, such as the Southern Photometric Local Universe Survey (S-PLUS), provide a unique opportunity to estimate atmospheric parameters and elemental abundances for a much larger number of sources compared to spectroscopic surveys.

Aims. Establish methodologies for extracting stellar atmospheric parameters and selected chemical abundances from S-PLUS photometric data, which cover approximately 3000 square degrees, by applying seven narrowband and five broad-band filters.

Methods. We used all 66 S-PLUS colors to estimate parameters based on three different training samples from the LAMOST, APOGEE, and GALAH surveys, applying Cost-Sensitive Neural Network (NN) and Random Forest (RF) algorithms. We kept stellar abundances that lacked corresponding absorption features in the S-PLUS filters to test for spurious correlations in our method. Furthermore, we evaluated the effectiveness of the NN and RF algorithms by using estimated T_{eff} and $\log g$ as input features to determine other stellar parameters and abundances. The NN approach consistently outperforms the RF technique on all parameters tested. Moreover, incorporating T_{eff} and $\log g$ leads to an improvement in the estimation accuracy by approximately 3%. We kept only parameters with a goodness-of-fit higher than 50%.

Results. Our methodology allowed reliable estimates for fundamental stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, and [Fe/H]) and elemental abundance ratios such as $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$, [Al/Fe], [C/Fe], [Li/Fe], and [Mg/Fe] for approximately 5 million stars across the Milky Way, with goodness-of-fit above 60%. We also obtained additional abundance ratios, including [Cu/Fe], [O/Fe], and [Si/Fe]. However, these ratios should be used cautiously due to their low accuracy or lack of a clear relationship with the S-PLUS filters. Validation of our estimations and methods was performed using star clusters, TESS (Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite) data, and J-PLUS (Javalambre Photometric Local Universe Survey) photometry, further demonstrating the robustness and accuracy of our approach.

Conclusions. By leveraging S-PLUS photometric data and advanced machine-learning techniques, we have established a robust framework for extracting fundamental stellar parameters and chemical abundances from medium- and narrowband photometric observations. This approach offers a cost-effective alternative to high-resolution spectroscopy, and the estimated parameters hold significant potential for future studies, particularly in classifying objects within our Milky Way or gaining insights into its various stellar populations.

Key words. Stars: fundamental parameters – Stars: abundances – Techniques: photometric – Surveys

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Appendix A: Training sets

The distribution of parameters identified in the GALAH and LAMOST datasets, the same as presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. A.1: Same as Fig. 4, but for GALAH sample.

Fig. A.2: Same as Fig. 4, but for LAMOST sample.

Table A.1: Selected architecture and hyperparameters of the CSNet.

Layer Type	Layer Description
Input	Size: 66x1
Convolutional	Dense: 224 neurons. Activation: linear
Convolutional	Dense: 320 neurons. Activation: linear
Convolutional	Dense: 608 neurons. Activation: linear
Convolutional	Dense: 320 neurons. Activation: linear
Convolutional	Dense: 128 neurons. Activation: linear
Output	Dense: 1 neuron. Activation: linear
Model Loss	mse

Appendix B: goodness-of-fit values.

Table B.1: Goodness-of-fit values for the three methodologies (ABC, see Section 3) employed in this study.

Flag	Survey	StarType	Parameter	RF(A)	NN(A)	RF(B)	NN(B)	RF(C)	NN(C)
00	APOGEE	Giant	T_{eff}	90.8	90.4
00	APOGEE	Dwarf	T_{eff}	95.1	97.2
00	LAMOST	Dwarf	T_{eff}	94.3	94.2
00	GALAH	Giant	T_{eff}	79.9	80.7
00	GALAH	Dwarf	T_{eff}	90.1	90.2
00	APOGEE	Giant	$\log g$	90.5	91.4	90.5	91.2
00	APOGEE	Dwarf	$\log g$	83.8	76.2	83.7	75.9
00	LAMOST	Dwarf	$\log g$	82.1	76.9	81.8	77.0
00	GALAH	Giant	$\log g$	78.4	81.9	78.2	82.0
00	GALAH	Dwarf	$\log g$	55.0	59.6	55.0	60.4
00	APOGEE	Giant	[Fe/H]	86.9	89.9	87.5	90.1	88.3	90.6
00	APOGEE	Dwarf	[Fe/H]	74.8	76.9	76.6	76.3	75.3	75.8
00	LAMOST	Dwarf	[Fe/H]	78.2	81.6	77.7	81.8	78.6	81.7
00	GALAH	Giant	[Fe/H]	78.5	84.0	80.0	84.8	83.8	87.2
00	GALAH	Dwarf	[Fe/H]	62.9	69.6	66.2	69.9	70.0	73.7
00	GALAH	Dwarf	[Li/Fe]	86.4	86.5	86.8	86.6	86.9	88.2
00	GALAH	Giant	[Li/Fe]	72.1	78.7	72.5	78.7	78.2	79.7
00	APOGEE	Giant	[Al/Fe]	75.2	75.6	75.7	75.7	77.9	76.0
00	APOGEE	Giant	$[\alpha/\text{M}]$	65.3	68.0	65.9	68.2	66.8	69.0
00	APOGEE	Giant	[C/Fe]	65.3	62.0	65.9	61.5	64.7	62.4
00	APOGEE	Giant	[Mg/Fe]	63.9	67.4	64.9	68.9	65.0	69.0
02	GALAH	Giant	[Cu/Fe]	61.3	62.5	62.0	63.3	59.5	63.8
02	APOGEE	Giant	[O/Fe]	56.1	59.0	57.1	58.9	57.7	58.4
01	APOGEE	Dwarf	[Mg/Fe]	54.6	55.7	55.6	56.3	54.6	55.1
01	APOGEE	Dwarf	$[\alpha/\text{M}]$	53.2	56.9	54.3	56.5	57.9	56.2
02	APOGEE	Giant	[Si/Fe]	57.6	58.8	57.9	59.4	57.6	59.4
02	APOGEE	Dwarf	[Si/Fe]	54.9	52.0	55.4	52.1	53.6	51.9

Appendix C: Importance Plots

This section presents the importance feature plots for some of the parameters analyzed in this work. The remaining plots can be requested from the authors.

Fig. C.1: The 20 primary features utilized for prediction are arranged in decreasing order. At the top of each diagram, the star type (giant or dwarf), data sample (LAMOST, APOGEE, or GALAH), and the elemental abundances are specified.

Appendix D: Plots of RF as function of NN

This section presents the plots illustrating RF as a function of NN estimations. These visualizations help to understand the relation and dependencies between RF and NN in our analysis.

Fig. D.1: Comparison of the predictions made on the testing sample between NN and RF models for the same stellar parameters, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. D.2: Continuation of the Fig. D.1.

Appendix E: Test set plots

This section features plots illustrating the testing set results for stellar parameters and elemental abundances using the Neural Network (NN) approach C.

Fig. E.1: Testing Set Results for Astrophysical Parameters (T_{eff} and $\log g$) in CSNet. Each plot features a one-to-one correlation between the parameters obtained from APOGEE, GALAH, and LAMOST surveys and those predicted by the neural network, as well as identity lines. Subplots display the residuals, representing the difference between the parameters obtained from the spectroscopic surveys and those predicted by the neural network. Blue and red dots correspond to dwarfs and giants, respectively. For both dwarfs and giants, the colorbar indicates the T_{eff} . The size of the symbols represents the value of $\log g$.

Fig. E.2: Continuation of Fig. E.1.

Fig. E.3: Continuation of Fig. E.1.

Fig. E.4: Continuation of Fig. E.1.

Fig. E.5: Continuation of Fig. E.1.

Appendix F: Catalog description

Description of the released table containing the estimated parameters obtained in this study. The catalog includes the following information:

Table F.1: Description of Parameters in the Catalog.

Parameter	Description
ID	Unique identifier for each celestial source.
Ra	Right Ascension coordinate of the source.
Dec	Declination coordinate of the source.
Elemental abundances	Parameters derived from CSNet approach.
[Fe/H]	Calculated abundance ratio of iron to hydrogen.
[α /M]	Calculated abundance ratio of α elements to iron.
[Al/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of aluminum to iron.
[C/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of carbon to iron.
[Li/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of lithium to iron.
[Mg/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of magnesium to iron.
[Cu/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of copper to iron.
[O/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of oxygen to iron.
[Si/Fe]	Calculated abundance ratio of silicon to iron.
Physical Parameters	Parameters obtained from <i>Gaia</i> data.
$\log g$	Logarithm of the surface gravity of the source.
T_{eff}	Effective temperature of the source.
Distance (<i>Gaia</i>)	Distance to the source calculated using data from the <i>Gaia</i> mission DR3.
Photometric Filters	Photometric measurements in various filters.
uJAVA	Photometric measurements in the uJAVA filter, corresponding to the u-band.
uJAVA (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the uJAVA filter measurements.
J0378	Photometric measurements in the J0378 filter.
J0378 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0378 filter measurements.
J0395	Photometric measurements in the J0395 filter.
J0395 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0395 filter measurements.
J0410	Photometric measurements in the J0410 filter.
J0410 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0410 filter measurements.
J0430	Photometric measurements in the J0430 filter.
J0430 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0430 filter measurements.
gSDSS	Photometric measurements in the gSDSS filter, corresponding to the g-band.
gSDSS (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the gSDSS filter measurements.
J0515	Photometric measurements in the J0515 filter.
J0515 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0515 filter measurements.
rSDSS	Photometric measurements in the rSDSS filter, corresponding to the r-band.
rSDSS (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the rSDSS filter measurements.
J0660	Photometric measurements in the J0660 filter.
J0660 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0660 filter measurements.
iSDSS	Photometric measurements in the iSDSS filter, corresponding to the i-band.
iSDSS (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the iSDSS filter measurements.
J0861	Photometric measurements in the J0861 filter.
J0861 (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the J0861 filter measurements.
zSDSS	Photometric measurements in the zSDSS filter, corresponding to the z-band.
zSDSS (Errors)	Errors or uncertainties associated with the zSDSS filter measurements.
FlagPhot	Flag (0-100): indicating % of features within the training set range, with 100 for all features within range.

Notes. The fundamental stellar parameters and chemical abundances were calculated separately using the APOGEE, GALAH, and LAMOST training samples and are kept in separate columns in the final catalog. The final catalog is available in electronic form at the CDS via anonymous ftp to cdsarc.u-strasbg.fr (200.54.220.98).

Appendix G: Comparison of [Fe/H] Values for Star Clusters

The following table presents a summary of the comparison between [Fe/H] values from various star clusters in our predicted sample and corresponding values from the literature.

Table G.1: Summary of the comparison of [Fe/H] values for various star clusters in our predicted sample with values from the literature.

Star Clusters		Giant Stars				Dwarf Stars								
ID	Literature		APOGEE		GALAH		APOGEE		GALAH		LAMOST			
	[Fe/H]	σ	N_G/N_{all}	[Fe/H]	σ	N_G/N_{all}	[Fe/H]	σ	N_D/N_{all}	[Fe/H]	σ	N_D/N_{all}	[Fe/H]	σ
^(a) NGC 7099 (M 30)	-2.29	0.07	81/339	-1.9	0.16
^(a) NGC 7089 (M 2)	-1.65	0.06	2/6	-1.43	0.16	1/6	-1.81	...	95/364	-1.39	0.18
^(a) NGC 7492	-1.64	0.13	2/2	-1.55	0.01	40/72	-1.37	0.19
^(a) NGC 3201	-1.46	0.02	7/233	-1.36	0.14	6/222	-1.25	0.13	859/5603	-1.34	0.23
^(b) NGC 288	-1.3	0.05	12/15	-1.15	0.16	10/14	-1.02	0.13	63/216	-0.98	0.12	226/5056	-1.07	0.09
^(c) NGC 1261	-1.27	0.08	17/20	-1.28	0.13	13/17	-1.15	0.1	53/149	-0.97	0.13	20/192	-0.95	0.11
^(d) NGC 362	-1.17	0.02	28/34	-1.06	0.14	26/32	-1.0	0.13	59/233	-0.88	0.11	16/134	-0.91	0.1
^(e) Pal 12	-1.00	0.10	7/7	-0.90	0.12	5/5	-0.83	0.11	13/25	-0.90	0.11	9/210	-0.88	0.12
^(b) NGC 104 (47Tuc)	-0.67	0.04	360/423	-0.66	0.18	364/418	-0.57	0.12	5512/7094	-0.67	0.17	4/23	-0.70	0.04
^(b) Berkeley 75	-0.34	0.05	2/2	-0.47	0.02	2/2	-0.32	0.03	1/5	-0.48	...	4377/5977	-0.61	0.15
^(b) Melotte 66	-0.32	0.03	5/5	-0.25	0.09	5/5	-0.2	0.1	34/40	-0.31	0.15	17/29	-0.68	0.18
^(b) Berkeley 33	-0.26	0.05	582/7918	-0.32	0.09
^(b) NGC 2335	-0.18	0.05	17/18	-0.09	0.09	3/7	-0.32	0.09
^(b) NGC 2354	-0.18	0.02	2/2	-0.2	0.17	36/40	-0.25	0.11
^(b) NGC 2547	-0.14	0.1	3/3	-0.21	0.03	1/6	-0.13	...
^(b) NGC 2287	-0.11	0.01	35/37	-0.03	0.08	19/24	-0.23	0.09
^(b) Tombaugh 1	-0.1	0.02	1/1	-0.27	...	1/1	-0.13	...	5/8	-0.17	0.1	2/2	-0.17	0.02
^(b) Ruprecht 4	-0.09	0.05	2/2	-0.25	0.01	2/2	-0.27	0.02	0.02	18/31	-0.14	0.09
^(m) NGC 2567	-0.09	0.02	4/4	-0.07	0.09
^(b) NGC 1901	-0.08	0.05	7/7	-0.12	0.12	5/6	-0.19	0.05
^(b) NGC 2482	-0.07	0.05	28/31	-0.06	0.09	5/5	-0.09	0.1
^(b) NGC 2447	-0.05	0.01	1/1	-0.01	...	28/34	-0.05	0.09
^(b) Collinder 140	-0.01	0.05	4/4	-0.16	0.02	3/4	-0.14	0.16
^(b) NGC 2451B	...	0.05	1/1	-0.12	...	4/4	-0.01	0.1
^(b) Blanco 1	0.03	0.07	6/10	-0.08	0.04	1/1	-0.11	...
^(b) NGC 2660	0.04	0.03	3/8	-0.04	0.05

Notes. The columns are as follows: (1) name of the star cluster, (2) [Fe/H] value from the literature, (3) standard deviation of [Fe/H] from the literature, (4 and 7) number of giant stars based on the probability (N_{all}) and those based on metallicities (N_G), (10, 13, and 16) number of dwarf stars based on the probability (N_{all}) and those based on metallicities (N_D), and their respective [Fe/H] values and standard deviations from our NN model for giant and dwarf stars from APOGEE, GALAH, and LAMOST. ^(a) Values from O'Malley & Chaboyer (2018). ^(b) Values from Carretta et al. (2009). ^(c) Values from Figuera Jaimes et al. (2013). ^(d) Values from Harris (1996). ^(e) Values from Muñoz et al. (2021). ^(f) Values from Wallerstein & Knapp (1998). ^(g) Values from Carraro et al. (2007). ^(h) Values from Netopil et al. (2016). ⁽ⁱ⁾ Values from Heiter et al. (2014). ^(j) Values from Sales Silva et al. (2016). ^(k) Values from Carraro et al. (2007). ^(m) Values from Tsantaki et al. (2023).